

An overview on Sex Sorted Semen

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Abstract

Artificially Inseminating cows with semen, separated by flow cytometry into fractions containing X-or Y-chromosome-bearing populations of sperm, allow scientists to skew the sex ratio of calves up to 90% of the desired sex. The disadvantage of using sexed semen is that we get a small insemination dose of functionally impaired sperm, exacerbated by damage during sorting and the result is reduced fertilising potential. With the commercial introduction of sexed semen, its use has been recommended for the insemination of heifers due to the higher fertility potential in them as compared to the lactating cows. The benefit and the rate of genetic gain would be greater through obtaining additionally high-value offsprings from superior cows using the sexed semen of elite bulls. Studies that have aimed to increase the efficiency of insemination with sexed semen have focused on the use of timed insemination programmes. This overview represents data from studies on sexed semen, factors related to pregnancy rates and the opportunities favouring an increase of pregnancies in dairy and beef cattle breeds.

Keywords- Sex sorted semen, farmers, fertility, chromosomes, production

Introduction

Semen having X or Y-chromosomes bearing sperm to produce progenies of predetermined, desired sex either female or male (80-90% accuracy) is termed as sexed semen. It is an assisted reproductive technology which can help to increase the potency of dairy herds' breeding programs [1].

The sorting process was pioneered by a reproductive physiologist, George E. Seidel of Colorado State University (CSU), US. Further research was done to find out the difference between the X and Y chromosomes [2]. Considering that difference as a hallmark, USDA (United States Department of Agriculture) researchers in Livermore, California, and Beltsville, Maryland developed a technology capable of separating the X chromosomes from Y. Later, which was named as "Beltsville Sperm sexing technology". A license was permitted to the Sexing Technologies (ST) of Texas and finally in 2001 the commercialization of sexed semen started [3]. After ST, ABS Global (formerly American Breeding Services) came up with a cutting-edge technology that kills 'Y' chromosome.

NDDB Dairy Services, a subsidiary of the National Dairy Development Board (NDDB) Anand, has developed indigenous sex-sorted semen technology to ensure birth of only female calves [4].

In March 2019, the country's first sex sorted semen production laboratory was established in Deep Frozen Semen Production Centre, Shyampur, Rishikesh financed by Rashtriya Gokul Mission scheme. Production of sexed semen of cattle (HF, Jersey, Sahiwal, Red Sindhi, Haryana and Gir) and buffaloes (Murrah) has started at the centre[5]. The technical partners in this endeavor is the Sexing Technologies, USA who has the original patent of the technology used.

Objectives of developing Sex Sorted Semen

Government approved Sex Sorted Semen scheme as it will target towards two basic objectives. It will help to increase the

productivity of cow and will indirectly decrease the number of unproductive male cattle because the practice of Amnapratha or letting loose of unproductive cattle is very common practice in India.

- A. India is the leading milk producer since 1998 along with its largest bovine population in the world. Milk production has increased from 17 million tons to 176.4 million tons during the period 1950-51 to 2017-18[6]. Dairy is also an important secondary source of income for many farmers in India. But due to rise in the population, urbanization and increased purchasing power of average population, the demand of milk and dairy products is accelerating. Thus, strategies are needed to be implemented in order to fulfill this demand, initialized by choosing calves of desired sex.
- B. The scheme has a potential to provide a permanent solution to stray cattle menace in next 2-4 years, with 90% fall in the number of male calves [7]. It is better not to be born than to lead a life full of sufferings. Many of us must have seen the stray bulls roaming here and there with open wounds on their body, laming or burn wound marks. Also, it's not easy to restrain them and take them to the nearest veterinary hospitals for treatment because of their massive body size and aggressive behavior towards humans.
- C. It will bring down the damage to crops and number of road accidents caused by stray animals. Overall, it will reduce the number of conflicts and deaths among both men as well as the stray cattles.

Technique behind Sex sorted semen

Sperm are distinguished on the basis of chromosomes. The sperm with X-chromosome (female) contains about 3.8% more DNA than the Y-chromosome (male) in cattle. This difference in their DNA content is used to sort the sperm.

Flow cytometry-based sorting is one of the most widely used effective method for sperm sorting. Principle of this method relies on the fact that the X-chromosome bearing sperm contain 3.8% more DNA than Y-chromosome bearing sperm. Before sorting, the sperm cells are stained with a florescent dye (Hoechest 33342) which binds with its DNA content without altering its

motility [8]. Bisbenzimidazole DNA-binding dye could also be used, as it binds with the DNA content of live sperms only [9]. Then these sperms are passed through the flow cytometer as drops of liquid containing a single sperm cell per droplet. X-chromosome bearing sperm shine brighter than Y when exposed to light as they have more DNA content. Then the laser and detector of cytometer will distinguish the sperm cells according to the amount of light they emit. Each sperm cell is then charged with either positive or negative charge. And the defected, damaged or dead sperm remain unchanged. Thus, these charged drops are deflected accordingly and collected. The uncharged droplets go straight.

Free flow electrophoresis [10], Percoll gradient/ Albumin Gradient/ Gradient swim down [11], Centrifugal counter current distribution [12], Identification of H-Y antigen [13], Genetic approaches etc[14]. are some other methods of sorting the sperm but further modifications are required for their commercial use.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of sex sorting using flow cytometry
Photo courtesy: Sexing Technologies, USA[15]

It's totally safe to use sexed semen straws for artificial insemination in field. But the concentration of sperm in conventional semen straw is far more than the sexed semen straws. Also, during sorting process some sperm get damaged. Overall, there is 10 to 15% decrease in the conception rates if we use sexed sperm semen as compared to conventional semen [16].

Advantages of using Sex sorted semen

- A. Producing only female calves, helps the farmers to save resources that would have been shared with unwanted males calves too.
- B. Production of more female calves will also increase the supply of replacement heifers.
- C. Increase in the opportunity to sell surplus heifers to other farmers/farms.
- D. Speed up genetic improvement:
 - a. Efficiency of progeny testing (PT) programme is increased
 - b. Efficiency of embryo transfer and IVF programme is increased

- E. Provides an economic and desirable way to increase herd strength without any risk of introducing diseases by purchasing heifers from outside (improves bio-security).
- F. This technique also enable us to sort out the viable sperm from dead, damaged or dying ones. Hence, the success rate of sorted semen at low concentration is much higher if compared to the conventional semen.
- G. By producing more female calves using sexed semen, less difficult births (dystocia) cases were observed, mainly among heifers. It was observed in a report that the cases of dystocia and stillbirth in heifers were 4.3% and 11.3% and for cow 0.9% and 2.7%, respectively by using sex sorted semen. While these values for conventional semen were 6% and 10.4% for heifers and 2.5% and 3.6 % for cows respectively. Hence a decline in the chances of dystocia by 28% in heifers and 64% in cows was seen by using sex sorted semen [17].

Limitations of using Sex sorted semen

A. Technological limitations:

- i. Sex sorting machine is costly.
- ii. The efficiency and speed attained by flow cytometry sorting is low.
- iii. The process of sorting semen requires highly skilled personnel.
- iv. Shear force, electrostatic charge, droplet formation and sudden stoppage cause high damage to the sperms [18].
- v. By the end of the process the wastage is around 50% of the viable sperms.
- vi. The freezing potential of sorted sperm is reduced to some extent [19].

B. Implementation limitations:

- i. High cost of the end product which is Rs. 1500-4500/- dose as compared to Rs. 15-20/- dose for conventional semen [20].
- ii. The conception rate with sex sorted semen is 10-15% less than the conventional semen. This factor will be more crucial in Indian condition considering low artificial insemination coverage (20-25%) and low conception rate with artificial insemination (25-35%)[21].
- iii. No standard operating procedure is available to perform the task of insemination using sorted semen. The concentration of sperm in sexed semen ranges between 2 and 4 million/dose whereas in conventional semen, it is 20 million/dose. Hence, in the field, there is a challenge to manage this lower sperm concentration under Indian conditions [22].

Commercially sex sorted semen is available only for HF and Jersey cattle's breeds in India [23].

Sexed semen is not available for any other Zebu breed of cattle and buffaloes.

Figure 2: A liquid nitrogen container containing sex sorted semen of HF crossbred in State Veterinary Hospital, Heera Nagar, Haldwani, Uttarakhand.

Success rate of sex sorted semen in Uttarakhand

An experiment was performed in Lohaghat block of Champawat district of Uttarakhand. Flow cytometric sorted sexed semen obtained from Uttarakhand Livestock Development Board (ULDB), Dehradun, was used to inseminate 70 cows (body weight lying between 300-400kg) in their first or second calving period. 40% cows conceived and out of these, 82.14% were cow calves while rest were bull calves. This clearly depicts that conception rate using sexed semen is low. This is also the reason why sexed semen straws are not the choice of farmers [24].

Conclusion

Science and technology are the double-edged sword. They have both pros and cons. And in this modern, developing and innovative society, science is that propellant which will lead us to the direction of development and well-being. Looking into its positive aspect, use of sex sorted semen will not only help our farmers to increase the productivity but will also help us to decrease the population of unwanted male calves. Farmers can now have the female calves having the characters of their desired sires and dams. But further, more researches are to be done in order to decrease the cost of its production and to improve the fertility rates using it.

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